

“ION MINCU” UNIVERSITY OF ARCHITECTURE AND URBANISM

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Uncomfortable Heritage

Adaptive Reuse Strategies for Industrial Building Reconversions

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0.1 Abstract

In recent years, the reconversion of industrial heritage sites has emerged as a critical endeavor in urban development and heritage conservation. This thesis delves into the adaptive reuse of industrial heritage sites, highlighting their significance in urban development and heritage conservation amidst the challenge of addressing "uncomfortable heritage." It investigates the dual task of preserving the historical essence of industrial buildings while repurposing them for new uses. Through comprehensive case studies, the research uncovers the intricacies of transforming industrial spaces, mindful of their historical and cultural importance and the occasional discomfort associated with their past functions. Employing qualitative methodologies, it examines diverse scenarios and strategies across various locations, seeking to distill core principles and lessons in industrial heritage regeneration. The study contributes insights into the complex interplay between industrial heritage, urban renewal, and cultural identity, advocating for a sensitive approach to conservation that respects the uneasy aspects of industrial heritage.

Ultimately, this thesis advocates for a nuanced approach to heritage conservation that acknowledges the inherent "uncomfortableness" of certain types of industrial heritage while embracing the transformative potential of adaptive reuse strategies in shaping sustainable and inclusive urban environments.

0.2 Executive Summary

1. Introduction:

Chapter 1 sets the stage by discussing the background and significance of industrial heritage, rationale for studying its reconversion, and research objectives and questions. It provides a structured overview of the thesis.

1.4 Current State of Research:

In Chapter 1.4, existing literature is critically examined, covering conceptual foundations, historical contexts, and theoretical frameworks.

1.5 Key Concepts and Definitions:

Key concepts and definitions are elucidated to establish a robust theoretical framework.

2. Connection to the Diploma Project

This chapter explores the link between the thesis and the Pre-Diploma Project, which focuses on repurposing the Old Municipal Abattoir in Bucharest into an interdisciplinary arts and culture park. Understanding this project's objectives provides valuable context for analyzing industrial building reconversions, underscoring practical applications of adaptive reuse principles in urban regeneration.

3. Description of the Phenomena:

Chapter 3 delves into the historical impact of industrialization and deindustrialization on urban landscapes (Section 3.1). It underscores the contemporary significance of adaptive reuse, focusing on sustainability concepts like the circular city and building, alongside relevant guidelines (Section 3.2). Additionally, local perspectives are explored, including public and authority attitudes towards industrial heritage (Section 3.3.a) and the local urban landscape's historical context (Section 3.3.b). These insights provide essential context for understanding the challenges and opportunities in industrial building reconversions for sustainable urban development.

4. Methodology:

Chapter 4 outlines the research approach (Section 4.1), emphasizing qualitative methods and case studies. Selection criteria for case studies (Section 4.2) and analysis parameters (Section 4.3) are meticulously defined to ensure methodological rigor.

5. Case Studies:

In Chapter 5, detailed descriptions of selected case study sites are provided, along with historical backgrounds, motivations for reconversion, and stakeholder involvement. Analytical assessments based on predefined criteria are presented highlighting successes, challenges, and lessons learned.

6. Analysis:

Chapter 6 offers a comparative analysis of case studies (Section 6.1), identifying common themes and evaluating the efficacy of reconversion strategies (Section 6.2). Sustainability considerations (Section 6.3) and long-term viability assessments (Section 6.4) are also discussed.

7. Discussion:

Chapter 7 interprets findings in relation to research objectives (Section 7.1), acknowledges study limitations, and suggests avenues for future research (Section 7.2).

8. Conclusion:

In Chapter 8, key findings are summarized.

9. References:

Chapter 9 lists all sources cited in the thesis, ensuring scholarly rigor and integrity.

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1. Introduction

1.1 Purpose of Work

The adaptive reuse of industrial heritage sites represents a pivotal intersection between preservation, sustainability, and urban development. This thesis delves into the multifaceted realm of reconverting industrial heritage. Additionally, the exploration of adaptive reuse extends to the context of "Uncomfortable Heritage," where sites with challenging historical narratives present unique opportunities and dilemmas. This inquiry aims to critically evaluate existing strategies and propose alternative approaches to address the complexities of uncomfortable heritage.

Background and Significance of Industrial Heritage

Industrial heritage, comprising factories, warehouses, and other industrial structures, holds historical and cultural significance. These edifices not only embody the legacy of industrialization but also serve as tangible reminders of societal progress and economic transformation. However, the decline of traditional industries has left many industrial sites abandoned or underutilized, presenting both challenges and opportunities for their adaptive reuse.

Rationale for Studying Reconversion of Industrial Heritage

The rationale for studying the reconversion of industrial heritage stems from the urgent need to address pressing global challenges, including climate change, urbanization, and heritage preservation. As outlined in Stone's work, "Undoing Buildings: Adaptive Reuse and Cultural Memory", the adaptive reuse of existing structures offers a proactive approach to sustainable development, wherein buildings are repurposed to accommodate evolving needs while retaining their cultural and historical significance. The author underlines that "issues of climate change and heritage have ensured that adaptation, instead of occupying the periphery of architectural concern, is now placed within the central ground of architectural practice"¹. However, the exploration of uncomfortable heritage introduces additional complexities, requiring a nuanced understanding of historical narratives, ethical considerations, and community engagement.

¹ Stone, Sally, *Undoing Buildings: Adaptive Reuse and Cultural Memory*, Routledge, 2020, ISBN 9781315397221, Introduction

1.2 Research Objectives

1.2.1 Overview of the Structure of the Thesis

This thesis aims to systematically examine various aspects of industrial heritage reconversion, particularly focusing on uncomfortable heritage through comprehensive case studies, theoretical analysis, and critical examination.

The structure of the thesis aims to explore the reconversion challenges and opportunities, critically addressing uncomfortable heritage and questioning current adaptive reuse paradigms.

1.2.2 Research Questions & Hypotheses

Questions

- a) What are the main challenges and dilemmas associated with the adaptive reuse of uncomfortable heritage sites, particularly in terms of preserving their historical significance while accommodating contemporary needs?
- b) What are the key factors influencing decision-making processes and stakeholder engagement in the reconversion of uncomfortable heritage sites?
- c) What are the most effective adaptive reuse strategies for industrial building sites classified as uncomfortable heritage, considering factors such as cultural sensitivity, environmental sustainability, and economic viability?
- d) How do different case studies of adaptive reuse projects on uncomfortable heritage sites compare in terms of their approaches, outcomes, and impacts on the surrounding communities?

Hypotheses

- a) The adaptive reuse of uncomfortable heritage sites poses significant challenges due to conflicting priorities between preservation, development, and community interests.
- b) Decision-making processes in the reconversion of uncomfortable heritage sites will be influenced by a complex interplay of factors, including regulatory frameworks, economic incentives, and public opinion.
- c) Adaptive reuse strategies that prioritize community engagement, sustainable design principles, and innovative programming will be more successful in addressing the dilemmas associated with uncomfortable heritage sites.

- d) Comparative analysis of case studies will reveal patterns and best practices for adaptive reuse strategies on uncomfortable heritage sites, providing insights into effective approaches and potential pitfalls to avoid.

1.3 Research Methods:

This thesis utilizes comparative analysis as its main research method, focusing on architectural adaptive reuse strategies for industrial heritage sites. By comparing different case studies, it provides a detailed look at various approaches, challenges, and results of transforming industrial buildings. This method extends beyond comparing aesthetics or functionality, including a comprehensive evaluation of the socio-economic, cultural, and environmental impacts of these architectural interventions. The goal is to understand both the architectural changes and their wider implications for industrial heritage conservation.

1.4 Current State of Research

The literature review plays a crucial role in this research by providing a comprehensive understanding of industrial heritage study and its relevance to the research topic. Through an examination of key texts and scholarly works, this section aims to define industrial heritage and elucidate its significance in contemporary discourse.

1.4.a) Definition and Significance of Industrial Heritage Study:

The significance of industrial heritage study lies in its impact on global economic and social change over the past three centuries. Industrialization has been a key driver of progress, enabling nations to transition from agrarian economies to prosperous industrial societies. This transformation has led to urbanization, improved living standards, and enhanced national power, shaping the human condition and habitat fundamentally. As the economic center of gravity shifts eastward, understanding industrial heritage becomes crucial in navigating the evolving world order.²

Cossons emphasizes that while the industrial landscape is often misunderstood, “it can also be a vivid reminder of how today’s world came to be the way it is, when industry employed

² Cossons, Neil, in *Industrial Heritage Retooled: The TICCIH Guide to Industrial Heritage Conservation*, edited by James Douet, Carnegie Publishing Ltd, 2012, ISBN 978-1-85936-218-1, Part 1: *Values and Meanings*, Chapter 1, *Why preserve the Industrial Heritage?*, [p. 6-16]

whole communities and provided the heartbeat for many towns and cities”³. As such, these historic industrial landscapes warrant careful attention and preservation.

The expansion of cultural heritage to include industrial buildings, particularly in the late 20th century, was shaped by changing attitudes towards industrial heritage, highlighted by global connectivity and agreements such as the UNESCO Convention⁴. This shift led to, as underlined by F. Choay in “L'Allégorie du patrimoine”, the emergence of a "Noah's Ark syndrome"⁵ wherein efforts were made to protect a wide range of architectural innovations from the 20th and late 20th centuries, including industrial structures, from the threats of destruction or abandonment.

Industrial heritage encompasses the physical remnants, locations, and activities associated with industrialization, reflecting the historical, social, and cultural significance of human endeavors. It provides insight into the origins of modern society, technological innovations, and the evolution of communities shaped by industrialization. By preserving industrial sites and landscapes, we maintain a tangible connection to our past, fostering a sense of identity and continuity amid rapid societal changes. Moreover, these sites offer economic opportunities through adaptive reuse and sustainable development strategies, serving as catalysts for tourism, creative industries, and community engagement while preserving the physical remnants of industrialization. Recognizing the value of industrial heritage honors the legacy of past generations while shaping a sustainable future.

1.4.b) Historical context:

The research on industrial heritage reconversion is influenced by seminal works and pivotal events shaping the field. The industrial revolution led to the widespread construction of factories and mills, but as industrial activities declined, questions arose about preserving and reusing these structures.

³ Cossons, Neil, *In Industrial Heritage Retooled: The TICCIH Guide to Industrial Heritage Conservation*, edited by James Douet, Carnegie Publishing Ltd, 2012, Part 1: *Values and Meanings*, Chapter 1, *Why preserve the Industrial Heritage?*, [p. 14]

⁴ UNESCO, *Convention concerning the Protection of the World Cultural and Natural Heritage*, accessed at <https://whc.unesco.org/en/convention/#:~:text=The%20Convention%20concerning%20the%20Protection%20of%20World%20Cultural%20and%20Natural%20Heritage,the%20Cultural%20and%20Natural%20Heritage.> [20.02.2024]

⁵ Choay, Françoise, *Alegoria Patrimoniului*, translated by Kázmér Kovács (Bucharest: Simetria, 1998), [pp. 132-134.]

The Venice Charter of 1964⁶, though focused on monuments, laid the foundation for discussions on industrial heritage preservation.

In recent decades, extensive research, global interdisciplinary cooperation, and community-driven initiatives have significantly enhanced the understanding and appreciation of industrial heritage. This progress has been bolstered by the establishment of a comprehensive set of international guidelines and references.

Key organizations like TICCIH⁷ and ICOMOS⁸, along with charters like The Nizhny Tagil Charter⁹ (2003) and The Dublin Principles¹⁰(2011), provided guidelines for industrial heritage preservation and reconversion.

1.4.c) Theoretical frameworks for understanding the body of the thesis:

The bibliography for this research has been curated to underpin the analysis framework for the case studies on industrial heritage reconversion. Key resources include Berens' insights on architectural and planning strategies for adaptive reuse in "Redeveloping Industrial Sites" (2010), Choay's examination of heritage within modern architectural practices in "L'Allégorie du patrimoine" (1996), and Douet's guidelines on conservation practices in "Industrial Heritage Re-Tooled" (2012). Additionally, Brooker and Stone's "ReReadings 2" (2019) delves into adaptive reuse and cultural memory, providing a theoretical basis for evaluating repurposing strategies. These works collectively inform the understanding of industrial heritage reconversion, offering a blend of strategic, cultural, and ethical perspectives essential for the case study analysis.

⁶International Council on Monuments and Sites (ICOMOS), *Venice Charter*, Accessed at https://www.icomos.org/images/DOCUMENTS/Charters/venice_e.pdf [20.02.2024]

⁷ International Committee for the Conservation of the Industrial Heritage (TICCIH), accessed at <https://ticcih.org/>. [20.02.2024]

⁸International Council on Monuments and Sites (ICOMOS), accessed at <https://www.icomos.org/en>. [20.02.2024]

⁹ The International Committee for the Conservation of Industrial Heritage (TICCIH), *Nizhny Tagil Charter for the Industrial Heritage*, accessed at <https://ticcih.org/wp-content/uploads/2013/04/NTagilCharter.pdf>. [20.02.2024]

¹⁰International Committee for the Conservation of Industrial Heritage (TICCIH) and International Council on Monuments and Sites (ICOMOS), *Joint Principles for the Preservation of Industrial Heritage Sites, Structures, Areas and Landscapes*, accessed at https://ticcih.org/wp-content/uploads/2013/10/GA2011_ICOMOS_TICCIH_joint_principles_EN_FR_final_20120110.pdf. [20.02.2024]

1.5 Key Concepts and Definitions:

This section clarifies and refines key concepts and definitions central to the study, essential for grasping the nuances of industrial heritage reconversion. Through definition, it seeks to provide a framework for analysis and discussion, enhancing the clarity and coherence of the thesis by defining critical terms related to the topic.

Uncomfortable Heritage in the context of industrial heritage:

In this case, uncomfortable heritage¹¹ refers to historical sites or buildings associated with industries or practices that evoke discomfort or unease due to their past activities or societal implications. Specifically, in the case of former abattoirs and meat markets, uncomfortable heritage arises from the history of meat production, which includes practices that may be considered ethically problematic, especially in light of contemporary debates on animal welfare and dietary choices.

However, these transformations often involve selective remembrance, where the more unpleasant aspects of the sites' histories are omitted or sanitized in favor of highlighting their architectural or cultural value.

In the process of adaptive reuse, industrial buildings such as, former slaughterhouses or meat markets, are repurposed for creative or cultural activities, such as contemporary art centers or event spaces, without explicit acknowledgment of their past functions. This approach can be seen as a missed opportunity to engage with the full complexity of these sites' histories, including the ethical and societal questions they raise about meat production and consumption.

Therefore, uncomfortable heritage encompasses not only the physical structures but also the ethical and cultural dimensions associated with their past activities. It prompts considerations about how to responsibly preserve and interpret these sites in ways that acknowledge their history while engaging with contemporary concerns and values.

¹¹ Wang Yiwen, Pendlebury John, *Uncomfortable heritage: how cities are repurposing former slaughterhouses*, <https://theconversation.com/uncomfortable-heritage-how-cities-are-repurposing-former-slaughterhouses-195688> [5.03.2024]

Adaptive reuse:

Adaptive reuse¹² repurposes existing buildings, like warehouses and factories, while preserving their historical or architectural significance. This acknowledges buildings' resilience to change and enables them to have "a number of different lives and achievable reincarnations"¹³. By adapting structures, cities maintain ties to the past while addressing current needs. However, this process requires careful balance between preservation and modernization, often involving structural adjustments. Furthermore, adaptive reuse supports sustainability goals by minimizing environmental impact and efficiently using resources.¹⁴

Reconversion:

Reconversion¹⁵, in the context of industrial heritage, refers to repurposing abandoned industrial sites for new uses while preserving their historical significance. It involves transforming these sites into functional spaces such as museums, commercial areas, educational institutions, or residential complexes to revitalize urban areas and promote economic growth. This process requires careful planning and collaboration to balance preservation with modern needs and constraints.

Brownfield:

The term "brownfield"¹⁶ describes land or buildings previously used but now abandoned, underused, or contaminated, often in urban or industrial settings. These sites can range from vacant factories to empty residential units and may be owned by various entities. Seen as opportunities for redevelopment within sustainable urban planning, brownfields, including

¹²Fragner, Benjamin., *Industrial Heritage Retooled: The TICCIH Guide to Industrial Heritage Conservation*, edited by James Douet, Carnegie Publishing Ltd, 2012, ISBN 978-1-85936-218-1, Chapter 14, *Adaptive Re-use*, [p.110-117].

¹³ Brooker Graeme, Stone Sally, "Introduction," in *Rereadings 2: Interior Architecture and the Design Principles of Remodelling Existing Buildings*, RIBA Publishing, 2018, ISBN 978 1 85946 581 3, Chapter 1.

¹⁴ Ibidem, Chapter 1.

"The reuse of existing buildings can now be considered a mainstream subject rather than a phenomenon. It is an approach that prioritizes an exploration of consuming less, exploiting more and utilizing what is to be found. This attitude values what we already have over the relentless and gratuitous pursuit of something new."

¹⁵ *Industrial Heritage Retooled: The TICCIH Guide to Industrial Heritage Conservation*, edited by James Douet, Carnegie Publishing Ltd, 2012, ISBN 978-1-85936-218-1, *Part III: Realizing the Potential*, [p. 85].

¹⁶ Stratton, Michael (ed.), *Industrial Buildings: Conservation and Regeneration*, E & FN Spon, 2000, ISBN 0-203-37507-6, [p. 2-26].

heritage industrial buildings, offer a chance to revitalize communities and promote sustainable development, rather than being cleared for new construction.¹⁷

Urban Regeneration:

Urban regeneration¹⁸, emerging in the 1990s in industrial cities, focuses on turning abandoned industrial sites into development opportunities. This process combines strategic planning, public-private partnerships, sustainability, and urban heritage enhancement to rejuvenate cities. It aims at economic development, job creation, and community revitalization, creating lively urban spaces through diverse funding, collaborative planning, and adaptable project implementation.

The following terms are defined according to the explanations offered by Graeme Brooker and Sally Stone in the book "Rereadings 2: Interior Architecture and the Design Principles of Remodelling Existing Buildings".

Intervention:

The strategy of intervention¹⁹ involves deliberate and purposeful alterations or additions made to existing structures to improve functionality, aesthetics, and usability while respecting their historical context. The term "intervention" originates from the Latin words "inter," meaning between, and "venire," meaning to come, suggesting an active involvement to create change and improvement.

Architectural interventions often encompass two main processes: stripping back and imposition of newly designed elements. Stripping back involves the removal of extraneous additions or unnecessary parts of the building, while the imposition includes the addition of new elements designed to integrate seamlessly with the original structure. These interventions aim to create a harmonious relationship between the old and the new, resulting in a single entity that respects the building's history while adapting it to contemporary needs.

¹⁷ Kirkwood, Niall. *Manufactured Sites: Integrating Technology and Design in Reclaimed Landscapes*, in *Manufactured Sites*, Taylor & Francis e-Library, 2005, ISBN 0-203-37390-1, Chapter 1

¹⁸ Preite, Massimo, *Industrial Heritage Retooled: The TICCIH Guide to Industrial Heritage Conservation*, edited by James Douet, Carnegie Publishing Ltd, 2012, ISBN 978-1-85936-218-1, Chapter 13. [p. 101-110]

¹⁹ Brooker Graeme, Stone Sally, *Rereadings 2: Interior Architecture and the Design Principles of Remodelling Existing Buildings*, RIBA Publishing, 2018, ISBN 978 1 85946 581 3, Chapter 2 "Strategies."

Key principles of an intervention strategy include: respect for context, integration, functionality and usability, sensitivity to history, innovation and creativity, community engagement.

Insertion:

Insertion²⁰ can be defined as the deliberate placement of new elements or structures within or alongside existing structures, creating a dynamic relationship between the old and the new. This act involves careful planning and consideration to create room for the new element, which may require removing unwanted detritus or clearing space. The insertion is not merely a passive addition but an active process that involves both subtractive and additive actions. The new element, while reliant on the host structure, maintains its own identity and is built to fit precisely within or around the existing space. Architectural insertions typically serve a specific function and may contrast with or complement the existing building, but they always maintain a distinct relationship with the original structure. The insertion can unify separate spaces, facilitate the needs of users, and contribute to the overall character and functionality of the building.

Installation:

Installation²¹ refers to the deliberate arrangement and placement of objects or elements within a specific space, typically for artistic or functional purposes. Installations are often characterized by their temporary or transient nature, as they can be removed or altered without causing lasting impact or damage to the host space. They can range from curated interior designs to large-scale structural interventions, such as the installation of a multi-storey steel structure within a historic building or the creation of a contemporary restaurant within an existing space. Installations may provoke emotional responses, encourage interaction with the environment, or serve as expressions of artistic or cultural significance. They can also be reversible, allowing for the restoration of the original space if needed. Overall, installations are dynamic and transformative interventions that engage with their surroundings and create unique experiences for viewers or users.

²⁰Brooker Graeme, Stone Sally, *Rereadings 2: Interior Architecture and the Design Principles of Remodelling Existing Buildings*, RIBA Publishing, 2018, ISBN 978 1 85946 581 3, Chapter 2, "Strategies."

Key characteristics of insertion include: deliberate and measured action, creation of space, dynamic interaction, specific functionality, distinct identity, defined relationship, specific functionality, distinctive design, integration with context, adaptation and transformation, enhanced user experience.

²¹Ibidem, Chapter 2, "Strategies."

Key characteristics of installation include: deliberate placement, self-contained and self-supporting structures, demountable, reversible, and exchangeable, experimental and investigative, transient or fleeting quality, reversible and non-damaging.

2. Connection to the Diploma Project

The themes investigated in this thesis lay the groundwork for the pre-diploma project, with case studies examining strategies and tactics pivotal for later diploma project transformations. These studies also delve into economic, social, and cultural models, integrating them into the project's theoretical framework.

A multifaceted qualitative research approach was used to explore the site's historical context, involving archival research, discussions with the site administrator, photographic documentation, and a thorough literature review.²² This strategy aimed to uncover the site's evolution, operational history, and architectural changes, placing it within a broader historical and cultural framework.

2.1 Short History Of The Site

The site of the Diploma project is situated at Splaiul Unirii 162 Boulevard in Bucharest, District 4, positioned on the right bank of the Dambovită River. The project centers on the transformation and reconversion of the former Municipal Abattoir located at this site.

Initially chosen in the mid-19th century, the location was strategically situated on the outskirts of the city, conveniently positioned on the right bank of the Dambovită River, where the river exited the city. This placement is crucial as the slaughterhouse operations relied heavily on water, with waste being directed downstream to manage pollution within the city, while awaiting for the installation of purification and disinfection stations.²³

The first measures to set up a modern slaughterhouse were taken in France in 1807, when it was officially required that the location of the slaughterhouses be near the water, on a vast land, allowing for further expansions. Bucharest's Abattoir followed the same logic.²⁴

In 1865, a contract was signed with Engineer Alexis Godillot for the construction of the slaughterhouse, inspired by the principles of the Paris slaughterhouses. By 1872, the

²² such as Liviu Chelcea's *Post-Industrial Bucharest: Memory, Deindustrialization, and Urban Regeneration* and *Description du Nouvel Abattoir de Bucarest: Construction, Agencement et Exploitation* by Nicolae Slăniceanu.

²³ Slăniceanu, Nicolae, *Description du Nouvel Abattoir de Bucarest: Construction, Agencement et Exploitation*, Imprimerie De La Cour Royale, F. Göbl Fils, 1914, p.5.

²⁴ Chelcea, Liviu, *Bucureștiul Post-Industrial: Memorie, Desindustrializare, Si Regenerare Urbana*. Polirom, 2008, ISBN 9789734609154, p. 312.

slaughterhouse was completed and put into operation, although subsequent years, starting in 1877, saw reports of irregularities from the city's Hygiene Council and veterinarians.²⁵

The early 20th century marked significant developments for the abattoir. Under the direction of architect Mandrea²⁶ additional facilities such as cattle markets and stables for various livestock were constructed. In 1910, after extensive research and documentation collection from abroad, including Germany, the overall plan for the new slaughterhouse was established²⁷. By 1913, further expansions were made, including the addition of a smelter building, sanitary department, and enlargement of the pig slaughtering hall.

Additionally, transportation played a vital role in the functioning of the abattoir. Animals were brought by train²⁸. Around 1906-1907, a project²⁹ was developed to extend the railway, connecting Obor-Filaret Stations to the Abattoir, passing through Carol I Park. Slăniceanu's book reveals that the project was ongoing in 1914.³⁰

However, construction progress was interrupted by the outbreak of World War I in 1914. Despite plans for further development, including additional buildings and facilities, construction remained halted until after the war. By 1921, the second Communal Slaughterhouse was finalized, modeled after European counterparts in Zürich, Frankfurt, and Breslau³¹, under the town engineers: Radu Ștefănescu, Ghermani, and Nemeș and architect Hârjău.

²⁵ Chelcea, Liviu, *Bucureștiul Post-Industrial: Memorie, Desindustrializare, Si Regenerare Urbana*. Polirom, 2008, ISBN 9789734609154, [p. 311].

²⁶ Slăniceanu, Nicolae, *Description du Nouvel Abattoir de Bucarest: Construction, Agencement et Exploitation*, Imprimerie De La Cour Royale, F. Göbl Fils, 1914,[p.4]

²⁷ Chelcea, Liviu, *Bucureștiul Post-Industrial: Memorie, Desindustrializare, Si Regenerare Urbana*. Polirom, 2008, ISBN 9789734609154, [p. 312].

²⁸Berceni de poveste, *Poveste cu trenul care făcea ciuu-ciuu prin Parcul Carol și pe Strada Lanariei*, <https://bercenidepoveste.ro/poveste-cu-trenul-care-facea-ciuu-ciuu-prin-parcul-carol-si-pe-strada-lanariei/> [20.02.2024]

²⁹ Bucharest City Archives, Bucharest City Hall Fund, Technical Service, 1905-1909, 205/1906, *Study and Project Regarding the Filaret-Abator railway line, 1906-1907*

³⁰ Slăniceanu, Nicolae, *Description du Nouvel Abattoir de Bucarest: Construction, Agencement et Exploitation*, Imprimerie De La Cour Royale, F. Göbl Fils, 1914,[p.5]

“On pourra relier bientôt l'Abattoir à la voie ferrée Obor-Filaret qui est en construction, et ainsi les bestiaux des wagons seront débarqués directement à l'Abattoir; le projet d'une voie ferrée allant de l'abattoir aux Halles centrales est étudié en même temps par la direction des Chemins de fer Roumains.”

³¹ Chelcea, Liviu, *Bucureștiul Post-Industrial: Memorie, Desindustrializare, Si Regenerare Urbana*. Polirom, 2008, ISBN 9789734609154, [p. 313.]

During the communist period from 1949 to 1989, the slaughterhouse underwent modifications, additions and annexations to accommodate increased production demands. However, after the revolution, meat processing activities ceased, and after 1990 the company that manages the land, Splai S.A., was privatized in full real estate litigation with the municipality.³² The buildings were repurposed, rented out to private companies, and underwent extensive modifications, including demolitions, partitioning of interior spaces, and adaptation for various commercial purposes such as workshops, storage spaces, restaurants, and other various businesses.³³

Fig. 1 Evolution of the Site

³² *Primăria Capitalei se luptă în instanță cu societatea Splai SA pentru terenul de mii de metri pătrați din Splaiul Unirii 162, unde fusese „Abatorul București”*, JustNews, November 15, 2021, accessed at: <https://justnews.ro/primaria-capitalei-se-bate-in-instanta-pentru-terenul-de-mii-de-metri-patrati-din-spaiul-unirii-162-unde-fusese-abatorul-bucuresti/> [25.02.2024]

Ion Alexandru, *Familia Videanu administrează afacerile dezvoltate de cenzorii fostului abator Splai SA*, Jurnalul, November 19, 2018, accessed at <https://jurnalul.ro/special-jurnalul/anchete/familia-videanu-administreaza-afacerile-dezvoltate-de-cenzorii-fostul-ui-abator-splai-sa-792493.html> [25.02.2024]

³³Chelcea, Liviu, *Bucureștiul Post-Industrial: Memorie, Desindustrializare, Si Regenerare Urbana*. Polirom, 2008, ISBN 9789734609154, p. 269. (translation made by the author)

“Here is a rental advertisement (for the Splaiul Unirii area) in which these efforts to rehabilitate the building and of increasing accessibility.

Industrial space, land of 4165 sq m, constructed area 2771 sq m, maximum h 6m, all utilities, prefabricated industrial building, compartmentalized, with insulated glass type foundations, strength structure made of reinforced concrete prefabs, perimeter closures made of heat-insulating panels, carpentry PVC with double glazing, interior partitions with plasterboard panels, screed floors with traffic-type linoleum. The hall was recently renovated, clad on the outside, the roof structure was redone, double glazed windows, a new heating plant and an air conditioning system were installed. Access to the interior is through two industrial doors, the space benefits from a ramp. On one of the sections of the hall there is also a 3.5 tf drawbridge (crane). An office space of approximately 250 square meters, sanitary facilities, changing rooms, showers was also arranged.”

Fig. 2

Site Plan 1888-188- First Version of The New Abattoir (left)
Site Plan-Architectural Survey by C.I.C.L.C.F Bucharest 1988 (right)

2.2 Short Overview of the Concept Proposal

The proposal endeavors to redevelop the former industrial site into an integrated Arts and Science Park, leveraging its historical significance while addressing contemporary urban challenges. As a preliminary step towards revitalizing the urban space, the surrounding wall and parasitic buildings erected post-1990, which cater to the varied businesses currently operating on the premises, will be removed.

Emphasizing connectivity and permeability, primary circulation pathways perpendicular to Splaiul Unirii Boulevard and Abatorului Boulevard are envisaged to disrupt the monolithic spatial configuration of existing structure.

A substantial setback from the street alignment is advocated to facilitate the establishment of a buffer zone, serving a dual purpose as both a botanical filter and a buffer against the vehicular traffic prevalent in the vicinity.

The healthy spontaneous vegetation present on the stables plot will be preserved, transforming the area into an expansive park, thereby fostering a linkage between the proposed initiative and Tineretului Park, as well as the adjacent public transportation hubs.

Preservation and adaptive reuse form the cornerstone of architectural interventions, particularly for iconic structures such as the Pig Slaughtering Hall and Cattle Slaughtering Hall, earmarked for conversion into versatile exhibition spaces accommodating both scientific and artistic endeavors.

Repurposing existing infrastructure is a key strategy, exemplified by the conversion of the former refrigeration plant into a multifunctional event space, complemented by vertical circulation towers facilitating access to proposed extensions. New constructions, primarily designated for the science center, are envisaged to harmonize with the site's historical fabric while accommodating contemporary programmatic requirements.

Interstitial spaces are conceived as dynamic hubs of cultural exchange, with a proposed cultural market repurposing the metallic structure of the former drying hall. Adaptive reuse extends to ancillary facilities, including repurposing the smelter as a library, the intestine processing workshop as an informal learning space, and the poultry slaughterhouse as a makerspace, offering the site a multifaceted identity instrumental to creative exploration.

Complementing architectural elements, thematic gardens are envisioned to serve as interactive landscapes promoting engagement, experimentation, and interdisciplinary discourse within the park. This approach seeks to foster a symbiotic relationship between built environment and green spaces, catalyzing social interaction, cultural enrichment, and intellectual inquiry within the reimagined urban realm.

Fig. 3 Diploma Project

3. Description of the Phenomenon

3.1. Historical Context of the industrialization and deindustrialization and its impact on the urban landscapes.

The Industrial Revolution marks a transformative period characterized by the mechanization of manufacturing processes and the proliferation of factory production. This epochal shift, initiated in Great Britain around 1760, caused widespread changes across societal, economic, and environmental landscapes over 250 years.³⁴

At its core, The Industrial Revolution marks the shift from agrarian societies to industrial ones, spurred by technological advances like the steam engine, improved transportation, and metallurgy. This era introduced mass production, division of labor, and urbanization. As industries adopted electricity and motor vehicles, urban landscapes transformed, leading to the growth of industrial complexes and factory towns.³⁵

During the nineteenth century, urban planners like Ebenezer Howard and Tony Garnier introduced innovative ideas to address the challenges of industrialization. Howard proposed Garden Cities, integrating housing, industry, and agriculture to combat urban decay, while Garnier's Cite Industrielle focused on regulated urban zones to separate work, living, and leisure areas. These pioneering concepts laid the foundation for modern zoning and city planning, emphasizing the need to balance industrial development with livability and sustainability.³⁶

As manufacturing techniques progressed, industrial structures evolved by incorporating novel forms, materials, such as cast iron, and construction methods to accommodate shifting demands.³⁷ This transformation had a profound impact on modern architecture, prioritizing minimalist designs and transparent showcases of materials and machinery.³⁸

³⁴ Albrecht, Helmuth, *What does the Industrial Revolution signify?*, in *Industrial Heritage Retooled: The TICCIH Guide to Industrial Heritage Conservation*, edited by James Douet, Carnegie Publishing Ltd, 2012, ISBN 978-1-85936-218-1, Part I, Chapter 2, [p.17-23].

³⁵ Stratton, Micheal (Ed.). *Industrial Buildings: Conservation and Regeneration*. London: E & FN Spon, 2000. ISBN 0-203-37507-6, Part 1, Chapter one, [p.10.]

³⁶ Berens, Carol, *Redeveloping Industrial Sites: A Guide for Architects, Planners, and Developers*, John Wiley & Sons, INC, 2011, ISBN 9780470649305, [p.30]

³⁷ Ibidem, Chapter 2.

³⁸ Ibidem, Chapter 2, [p. 35].

The diffusion of British technology to Europe and North America catalyzed industrial expansion, with each region experiencing unique trajectories shaped by local contexts and state interventions.

In the late 20th century, traditional manufacturing industries in Europe started declining. The Oil Crisis of 1973 ended the postwar boom, causing plant closures, site clearances, and a global economic crisis. Deindustrialization accelerated due to globalization, technological progress, and shifting consumer preferences, leading to factory closures, job cuts, and the abandonment of industrial sites across Europe.³⁹

Deindustrialization caused the decline of vibrant industrial cities, leaving behind abandoned factories, brownfield sites, and crumbling infrastructure. Moreover, urban areas once driven by industry encountered socio-economic issues like unemployment, poverty, and social exclusion.⁴⁰

The environmental awareness movement, starting in the 1970s, led to a shift in addressing environmental concerns, sparked by events like the Stockholm Conference on the Human Environment. Grassroots groups like Greenpeace emerged, opposing nuclear energy and advocating for environmental protection. Governments responded with regulations, reducing overt environmental offenses. However, the issue of abandoned industrial sites remained, requiring integrated solutions beyond demolition. Concurrently, historians recognized the historical value of these sites, leading to their adaptive reuse into various functional spaces.⁴¹

Berens, Carol, *Redeveloping Industrial Sites: A Guide for Architects, Planners, and Developers*, John Wiley & Sons, INC, 2011, ISBN 9780470649305

Berens underlines that industry and its processes have long served as a wellspring of inspiration for artists and architects alike, “from the screed against ornament by Adolf Loos to the design explorations of the Bauhaus and the sleek lines of the International Style to the explicit expression of construction elements in the work of Rogers Stirk Harbour + Partners”.

³⁹ Stratton, Micheal (Ed.). *Industrial Buildings: Conservation and Regeneration*. London: E & FN Spon, 2000. ISBN 0-203-37507-6, Part 1, Chapter one, [pp. 10-12].

⁴⁰ Ibidem, Part 1, Chapter one, [p.11].

⁴¹ Tempel, Norbert, *Post-industrial landscapes*, in *Industrial Heritage Retooled: The TICCIH Guide to Industrial Heritage Conservation*, edited by James Douet, Carnegie Publishing Ltd, 2012, ISBN 978-1-85936-218-1, Part III, Chapter 19, [p.145].

3.2. The importance of adaptive reuse in the current context:

Adaptive reuse is pivotal in Europe's efforts to combat sustainability challenges like global climate change and urbanization. By repurposing historic structures, it curbs environmental impact from new construction while safeguarding cultural heritage and urban identity, in line with sustainable development objectives and circular economy principles. This approach extends building and material lifespans, reduces resource consumption, and minimizes waste generation, contributing to circular city models and energy conservation, saving energy by utilizing the non-recoverable energy embedded in buildings. This retained "embodied energy" includes all energy expended in construction, including fuel, materials, and labor.⁴²

Moreover, adaptive reuse revitalizes urban areas, fosters mixed-use developments, and cultivates vibrant, inclusive communities that bolster social cohesion and economic growth. Aligning with the European Union's goals⁴³ of resource efficiency and emission reduction, these practices preserve collective memory, bridging past and present urban development while nurturing a sense of place and identity, thus enriching European cities culturally for current and future generations⁴⁴.

3.3 Brief description of the phenomenon on a local level

3.3.a) Historical context of the industrialization and deindustrialization and its impact on the local urban landscapes.

Romania's industrialization and deindustrialization have shaped its urban landscapes and cultural heritage significantly. Despite starting later than other parts of Europe, Romania's industrial activities have a rich history spanning centuries, featuring diverse and distinctive industrial architecture, technology, and aesthetics, from proto-industrial forms to modern industrial complexes.

The industrialization in Romania started in the 19th century, driven by resource exploitation like mining and the establishment of industrial centers. Political changes and foreign

⁴²Watson, Mark, *Adaptive re-use and embodied energy*, in *Industrial Heritage Retooled: The TICCIH Guide to Industrial Heritage Conservation*, edited by James Douet, Carnegie Publishing Ltd, 2012, ISBN 978-1-85936-218-1, Part III, Chapter 18, p.136.

⁴³Deal, EU Green. *The European Green Deal. Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the European Council, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions*. Brussels, 2020,

https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/priorities-2019-2024/european-green-deal_en [20.05.2024]

⁴⁴European Commission, Directorate-General for Education, Youth, Sport and Culture, *Strengthening cultural heritage resilience for climate change – Where the European Green Deal meets cultural heritage*, Publications Office of the European Union, 2022, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2766/44688>

influence, especially from the Austro-Hungarian Empire, also shaped this landscape. The communist era further accelerated industrial development, leading to the creation of large-scale industrial centers nationwide.⁴⁵

Industrial architecture has evolved over time, balancing functional needs with aesthetic considerations. Examples⁴⁶ like Assan's Mill, Filaret Gasworks, Former Customs Warehouse, and colony houses in Reșița, Petroșani, and Roșia Montană showcase Romania's industrial heritage. While some are recognized as historical monuments for their architectural significance, many sites face abandonment and decay, threatening Romania's cultural heritage.

Romania's industrial heritage showcases architectural diversity, with distinct typologies for activities like mining, steel production, and textiles. The evolution of transportation, notably railways, in the 19th and early 20th centuries also influenced the landscape, leading to unique structures like bridges, railway stations, and industrial infrastructure.⁴⁷

3.3.b) Attitudes of the general public and local authorities regarding industrial heritage.

There's a growing trend to repurpose abandoned industrial buildings for economic or cultural ventures like museums and theaters. Berens highlights how the land requirements of early industries shape the redevelopment of industrial sites. Industries relied on access to water sources for powering machinery, leading to the development of cities around these economic centers. Consequently, waterfront areas in industrial cities, once reserved for factories, are now in high demand for recreational and residential purposes.⁴⁸

Indeed, while this approach holds promise, it also raises concerns about gentrification. Effectively addressing this challenge necessitates comprehensive strategies at both the city-wide level and within each specific redevelopment initiative, emphasizing bottom-up approaches throughout all stages of development.

⁴⁵ Merciu, F. C., Merciu, G. L., & Stoian, D. *Patrimoniul Arhitectural Industrial Românesc – Trecut Și Prezent*. Urbanism. Arhitectură. Construcții, 2012, 3(3), [pp 28-29].

⁴⁶SOS Patrimoniu, *Patrimoniul industrial al Capitalei, lăsat la mila timpului*, SOS Patrimoniu, <https://www.sospatrimoniu.ro/sos-articole/patrimoniul-industrial/item/135-patrimoniul-industrial-al-capitalei-lasat-la-mila-timpului> [20.05.2024]

⁴⁷ Merciu, F. C., Merciu, G. L., & Stoian, D., *Patrimoniul Arhitectural Industrial Românesc – Trecut Și Prezent*. Urbanism. Arhitectură. Construcții, 2012, 3(3), [p. 29].

⁴⁸ Berens, Carol, *Redeveloping Industrial Sites: A Guide for Architects, Planners, and Developers*, John Wiley & Sons, INC, 2011, [p.12].

Architects and planners now assume the architectural and cultural significance of industrial heritage, aiming to blend it into modern cityscapes. Initiatives like the OAR's Multiplexity⁴⁹ competition in Timișoara underscore this trend. Additionally, civic groups and NGOs such as PlusMinus Association, Industrial Archaeology Association, Make a Point and Zeppelin are actively involved in researching, educating, and repurposing industrial heritage sites.⁵⁰

Attitudes toward preserving industrial heritage vary widely, among the general public and local authorities, with some recognizing its cultural importance while others prioritize economic development. Consequently, many sites are neglected and at risk of disappearing due to lack of maintenance. Preservation efforts in Romania encounter challenges like funding limitations and bureaucratic obstacles, or disputes over property ownership. Additionally, there is the challenge of garnering community support for preservation initiatives.⁵¹

Despite these hurdles, there have been successful projects repurposing industrial sites for cultural or economic use. However, such initiatives are relatively few compared to the country's overall industrial heritage landscape.⁵²

Preserving industrial heritage in Romania is vital for maintaining architectural coherence, honoring its industrial past, and strengthening cultural identity. Balancing economic growth with heritage preservation presents challenges, necessitating coordinated efforts among local authorities, preservation organizations, and local communities.

⁴⁹ OAR - Ordinul Arhitecților din România, *Centrul pentru Artă, Tehnologie și Experiment: Multiplexity Timișoara*, OAR - Ordinul Arhitecților din România, <https://oar.archi/concursuri/oar/centrul-pentru-arta-tehnologie-si-experiment-multiplexity-timisoara/> [20.02.2024]

⁵⁰ Din Alexandra, Diaconu Ioana, *Patrimoniul industrial: Asociația PlusMinus I Asociația pentru Arheologie Industrială I Make a Point I Zeppelin*, IGLOO, <https://www.igloo.ro/initiative-de-salvgardare-a-patrimoniului-industrial-romanesc/> [21.02.2024]

⁵¹ Cossons, Neil, *Industrial Heritage Retooled: The TICCIH Guide to Industrial Heritage Conservation*, edited by James Douet, Carnegie Publishing Ltd, 2012, Part 1: *Values and Meanings*, Chapter 1, *Why preserve the Industrial Heritage?*, [p. 8].

Cossons emphasizes that, furthermore, advocating for the preservation of a defunct industrial site based solely on traditional heritage values may not always resonate with a community facing economic challenges such as collapse or high unemployment rates. Alternatively, while the community may find the concept appealing, offering as it might the chance of capturing something of their former spirit and pride” the harsh economic realities often render traditional preservation methods unfeasible.

⁵² Merciu, F. C., Merciu, G. L., & Stoian, D. *Patrimoniul Arhitectural Industrial Românesc – Trecut Și Prezent*. Urbanism. Arhitectură. Construcții, 2012, 3(3), [p.33].

4. Methodology

4.1. Qualitative Research: Case Studies

The research for this thesis employs qualitative methods, primarily through case studies. Initially, a single-case study and instrumental case study approach will be used to analyze each project based on established criteria in Chapter 5. Subsequently, a comparative approach will be applied in the following chapter to identify similarities, differences, and assess the effectiveness, sustainability, and long-term viability of the projects.

4.2. Criteria of selection of case studies

In the analysis of case studies, the initial focus will be on a comprehensive examination of Matadero Madrid, followed by a detailed investigation into specific instances within the complex. Matadero Madrid stands as a prominent example within the European cultural and architectural context. The emphasis will be on selecting case studies demonstrating positive outcomes and employing varied intervention strategies. Moreover, these case studies will be evaluated in terms of community revitalization, economic regeneration, and the preservation of cultural identity, with the aim of determining their effectiveness in promoting sustainable development and inclusive growth.

4.3. Selection criteria for the analysis of the case studies:

To ensure a comprehensive analysis of the case studies, various criteria will be established to guide the examination of the projects such as: interventions at the urban scale, public space, space typologies, architectural value, type of strategy, structure, materiality, expressivity, community impact and involvement and economic factors. These criteria aim to demonstrate best practices, and innovative solutions as well as aid the understanding of future challenges.

5. Case Studies

5.1 Matadero Contemporary Art Center, Madrid

The upcoming case study will initially undergo a comprehensive analysis based on various criteria applicable to the entire complex. Subsequently, the examination will be subdivided into three smaller case studies focusing on specific interventions, which collectively form a cohesive system, namely: **Intermediae** by Arturo Franco, **Nave 16** by Carnicero, Vila and Virseda, and **Casa del Lector** by Ensamble Studio.

The Matadero Art Center in Madrid, Spain, serves as a significant case study site in the exploration of uncomfortable industrial heritage. Established on the grounds of a former slaughterhouse complex, the Matadero Art Center epitomizes the adaptive reuse of industrial infrastructure for cultural purposes.

Fig. 4 Photo of Matadero Madrid and Placement of the Case Studies

Image source available online at *Arquitectura Viva, Centro de Creación Matadero*. [26.03.2024].

Fig.5 Map Of Matadero Madrid And Its Cultural Facilities

Image source: Matadero Madrid Official Website.

The Matadero Art Center⁵³ occupies a sprawling industrial complex spanning approximately 165,415 square meters. Located along the Manzanares River, the site comprises a series of interconnected buildings, including former slaughterhouses, livestock pavilions, and auxiliary structures. These architectural elements reflect the industrial character of the site and provide a unique backdrop for artistic expression and cultural activities.⁵⁴

Historical Background of the Industrial Site:

The history of the Matadero Art Center traces back to the early 20th century when it operated as Madrid's primary municipal slaughterhouse complex. The original architect of Matadero Madrid, was Luis Bellido González, the municipal architect at that time. He designed the

⁵³Matadero Madrid, *Discover Matadero Madrid*, accessed at <https://www.mataderomadrid.org/en/discover> [26.03.2024]

Matadero Madrid offers a diverse range of cultural activities, including exhibitions, theater performances, festivals, music events, film screenings, conferences, workshops, and educational programs for families. The center's activities are overseen by Matadero Madrid's artistic direction, along with the Coordination Office and public programs like Intermediae, Medialab, and the Center for Artists in Residence. Additionally, it collaborates with public centers such as Cineteca Madrid and Naves del Español, as well as private partners including Central de Diseño (managed by the Diseño de Madrid-DIMAD Foundation), Extension AVAM (managed by Artistas Visuales Asociados de Madrid), Casa del Lector (the German Sánchez-Ruipérez Foundation), and the Center for Immersive Experiences (MAD. Madrid Artes Digitales).

⁵⁴ Arquitectura Viva, *Centro de Creación Matadero*, Arquitectura Viva, accessed at <https://arquitecturaviva.com/obras/centro-de-creacion-matadero> [26.03.2024]

complex, after the German model⁵⁵, in what's called the Neomudéjar style⁵⁶, and it was inaugurated in 1923.

The decision on the placement of the new Slaughterhouse and Market of cattle involved careful consideration of factors such as accessibility, sanitation, and potential for future expansion, akin to those considered for Municipal Abattoirs across Europe. After considering various locations, architect Luis Bellido selected the southeastern sector of the Dehesa de la Arganzuela⁵⁷ for its favorable attributes, ample space, and proximity to railways and water. This area provided 165,415 m² of space for the municipal complex, with potential for future expansions or agricultural use. The overall plan aimed to optimize the site's layout and infrastructure for efficient operations and potential growth.

Serving the city's burgeoning population, the site played a crucial role in meat processing and distribution for decades. However, with advancements in transportation and changing urban dynamics, the slaughterhouse ceased operations in the late 20th century, leading to the abandonment of the site.

⁵⁵ Servicio Histórico Coam, *Memoria Histórica Para El Proyecto De Rehabilitación Del Antiguo Matadero Municipal De Madrid, El Sector Meridional*, Madrid: COAM, enero, 2005, [pp. 29-30].

German abattoirs, known for their meticulous organization and efficiency, greatly influenced the design of the slaughterhouse operations. Bellido's visits to modern slaughterhouses in cities like Berlin, Cologne, Breslau, Offenbach and Leipzig provided insights into the benefits of government regulations implemented since 1868, including the prohibition of private slaughterhouses. German slaughterhouses were divided into two main sections: the slaughterhouse and the livestock market, each with specialized areas for different stages of processing. The emphasis on precision, order, and hygiene in German establishments contrasted with practices in Spain. The interior spaces were optimized for efficiency, with diaphanous warehouses and specialized areas for different stages of the slaughtering process. Matadero Madrid incorporated modern features such as refrigerated chambers and mechanical equipment, reflecting the progressive ideas observed in German slaughterhouses.

⁵⁶ *Neo-Mudéjar, A Spanish Architectural Style*, Madrid Visitors & Convention Bureau, accessed at: <https://www.esmadrid.com/en/neo-mudejar-spanish-architectural-style#:~:text=Main%20characteristics%20of%20Neo%2DMud%C3%A9jar,surfaces%20with%20consistent%20geometric%20motifs.> [27.03.2024]

Neo-Mudéjar architecture is a Spanish architectural style that emerged in the late 19th and early 20th centuries, characterized by the use of soft materials like brick, ceramic, stucco, and tile. It features exposed brick with intricate geometric patterns, alternating with masonry in a technique known as *parejo toledano* (toledo bond). Interiors often include ribbed vaults or coffered wood ceilings, along with vividly colored ceramics. While incorporating elements from Hispano-Islamic architecture, Neo-Mudéjar buildings also integrate Christian traditions such as symmetrical façades and Latin cross plans in churches. Neo-Mudéjar architecture was commonly used for various structures including bullrings, railway stations, schools, factories, and homes.

⁵⁷ *Dehesa de Arganzuela*, Wikipedia, accessed at https://es.wikipedia.org/wiki/Dehesa_de_Arganzuela. [27.03.2024]

Stretching from the Toledo bridge to the Paseo de Yeserías, it occupied the area now traversed by the M-30 highway. This land was utilized as grazing grounds for cattle destined for slaughter at the nearby old town slaughterhouse, beginning in the 16th century.

Fig.6 Historic Image of Matadero Madrid

Matadero y Mercado de Ganados en Memoria. Información sobre la ciudad. 1929, Madrid: Ayuntamiento de Madrid, 1929.

Process and Motivations for Reconversion:

The decision for preservation of the Matadero y Mercado de Ganados de Madrid complex was influenced by its historical significance and the cultural movement advocating for the protection of architectural heritage. Despite facing obsolescence and political pressure for demolition, the site remained integral to Madrid's cultural landscape. Legislation, such as the 1967 Law of Arganzuela, aimed at converting adjacent land into green spaces, posed a threat to the complex's existence. However, growing cultural appreciation for architectural heritage preservation led to a shift in public sentiment. Initially, there were modest efforts to protect certain buildings within the complex, such as the Central Pavilion. Eventually, broader preservation measures were implemented, culminating in the preservation of the majority of the complex.⁵⁸ Overall, the decision to preserve the Matadero y Mercado de Ganados de Madrid complex reflected a broader societal shift towards valuing and protecting architectural heritage, and in 1997 it was included in the Catalog of Protected Buildings of the Plan General of Urban Planning of Madrid.

⁵⁸ *Matadero Madrid*, Wikipedia, accessed at: https://es.wikipedia.org/wiki/Matadero_Madrid [27.03.2024]

Various proposals emerged for alternative uses of the space, including plans for a Museum of Architecture, municipal libraries, multiplex cinemas, and a shopping center. However, the slaughterhouse buildings remained abandoned and inaccessible to the public. Some environmental actions led to the creation of what became known as the Parque del Matadero. Conversion plans were considered for buildings like the Clock House, while unsuccessful attempts were made to establish the regional television headquarters and the National University of Distance Education in other areas of the complex.

The reconversion process involved extensive planning, architectural interventions, and stakeholder consultations to ensure the preservation of historical heritage while accommodating contemporary uses.⁵⁹

Another significant factor was the urban fabric's requalification surrounding the Matadero, extending the city's centrality towards the Manzanares River. This initiative aimed to enhance an area traditionally marginalized, thereby contributing to the broader urban revitalization efforts.

Guillermo Costa's first reconversion project at Matadero Madrid in the '90s marked a significant milestone in the site's transformation. Costa's vision breathed new life into the industrial complex, reimagining its spaces for cultural and artistic purposes, stripping away the interior partitioning walls of the halls.⁶⁰ One of the most memorable interventions was the transformation of the market warehouse into a 19th century style greenhouse, with tropical and subtropical zones.

Stakeholders Involved in the Reconversion Process and Community Impact:

The reconversion of the Matadero Art Center engaged a broad spectrum of stakeholders, including municipal authorities, cultural institutions, urban planners, architects, artists, residents, and community groups. Collaborative efforts were crucial for shaping the site's transformation vision, securing support, and integrating diverse perspectives into redevelopment plans. This inclusive approach contributed to the success of the Matadero Art Center as a prominent cultural landmark in Madrid.

Economic Factors:

The estimated cost of redeveloping Matadero Madrid into a cultural center ranges from €60 million to €80 million, covering architectural renovations, infrastructure upgrades, programming, and operational costs. While these figures are approximate and funding sources may have varied, the project aimed to secure support from both public and private sectors to ensure long-term benefits, including cultural enrichment, tourism revenue, and community development.

⁵⁹ Servicio Histórico Coam, *Memoria Histórica Para El Proyecto De Rehabilitación Del Antiguo Matadero Municipal De Madrid, El Sector Meridional*, Madrid: COAM, enero, 2005, [pp. 53-58].

⁶⁰ *Ibidem*, [pp.60-69]

5.1.2 Analysis based on selected criteria:

Matadero Madrid in the Urban Scene:

Fig.7 Satellite View of Matadero Madrid and Madrid Río Park
Image source: Google Earth.

Matadero Madrid is located in the Arganzuela district of Madrid's Legazpi quarter. Specifically, it is situated along the banks of the Manzanares River, which runs through the southern part of the city and next to Madrid Río Park⁶¹, a vast leisure and cultural spot parallel to the river. Historically, the district was known for its industrial activities, but this is precisely the main reason why the area is such a successful recreation area.⁶²

Through integrated vision and planning, the municipality successfully transformed the area with several interventions into a cohesive system functioning as a vast leisure area.

The Madrid Río Park, features 17 play areas for children, Madrid Río Beach for cooling off in summer, and bio-healthy circuits for adults, while Matadero Madrid offers cultural highlights.

In terms of its placement within the city, Matadero Madrid occupies a significant area of land, reflecting its former function as a large-scale industrial site. However, its adaptive reuse into a cultural center has transformed it into a dynamic space that integrates seamlessly with its urban surroundings, boosting the quality of life within the neighborhood. Today,

⁶¹ *Madrid Río*, Wikipedia, accessed at: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Madrid_R%C3%ADo [27.03.2024]

The park was built following the burial of the M-30 bypass road in the area. The project was led by architect Ginés Garrido, following the win of the international ideas competition organized by the Madrid City Council in 2005 to redevelop the area.

⁶² Berens, Carol. *Redeveloping Industrial Sites: A Guide for Architects, Planners, and Developers*, John Wiley & Sons, INC, 2011, ISBN 9780470649305, p.12.

As Berens highlights in her book, the former purpose of the site and its dependence on water, makes it now that those areas within the city are the most in demand for recreational functions or residential areas. The same thing happened in the case of Matadero Madrid, Its former function made it a suitable place for the development of a cultural park.

Matadero Madrid stands as a prominent cultural hub within the city, contributing to Madrid's vibrant arts scene.

Fig.8 View from Madrid RíoPark towards Matadero Madrid (left).

Image source: Matadero Madrid Official Website.

Fig.9 Aerial View of Madrid Río Park and Manzanares River (Right).

Photo by Nauris, accessed at Adobe Stock.

Public Space:

In regard to public space, the inner square of the complex primarily consists of a paved urban square, with a focus on delineating various pathways and connections between different halls. Plaza Matadero and Calle Matadero⁶³, the two main pedestrian spaces, designed by Ginés Garrido, Carlos Rubio and Fernando Porrás, serve as the cultural hub's central gathering places. Accessible from various points including Plaza de Legazpi and Madrid Río Park, they facilitate the flow between Matadero's different institutions.

Fig.10 Photo of Plaza Matadero

Image source: Matadero Madrid on Flickr.

⁶³Matadero Madrid, *Arquitectura*, accessed at <https://www.mataderomadrid.org/arquitectura>. [25.03.2024]

The "Escaravox" project by Andrés Jaque at Matadero Madrid reimagines public space through innovative design⁶⁴, through a series of installations. It introduces dynamic elements such as movable platforms and sound installations, creating a flexible environment that encourages social interaction and cultural engagement. This transformation enhances the usability and vibrancy of the public square, turning it into a dynamic hub for the community.⁶⁵

Fig. 11 Aerial photo of Escaravox by Andrés Jaque
Photo by Miguel de Guzmán (2014).

Fig.12 Various Uses of Escaravox (from left to right: picnic table, events screen, events pavilion). Photos by Miguel de Guzmán (2014).

⁶⁴ Public Space, *Escaravox*, accessed at <https://www.publicspace.org/ca/obres/-/project/j084-escaravox> [28.03.2024]

The equipment, costing about €100,000, is crafted from recycled industrial materials like agricultural irrigation fixtures, photovoltaic panels, supermarket carts, synthetic crop covers, construction debris sacks, and restaurant plastic chairs. These forty-two-meter-long tents, equipped with pneumatic wheels, are versatile in movement and orientation. One tent is furnished with computers and audiovisual systems for video projections, while the other features lighting and sound systems for performances.

⁶⁵

Office for Political Innovation, *Escaravox*, accessed at <https://officeforpoliticalinnovation.com/work/escaravox/> [28.03.2024]

Andrés Jaque Architects, *Escaravox*, ArchDaily, accessed at <https://www.archdaily.com/270438/escaravox-andres-jaque-architects> [28.03.2024]

Fig.13 Diagrams exemplifying the versatility of Escaravox by Andrés Jaque.

Sustainability:

The sustainability of the Matadero Madrid project is evident in its adaptive reuse of industrial buildings, preserving historical heritage while minimizing new construction. Energy-efficient systems like lighting and HVAC reduce energy consumption. Culturally, it promotes heritage preservation and community cohesion. Economically, it creates jobs, boosts tourism, and supports local businesses. Socially, it offers inclusive spaces for cultural activities, fostering interaction and dialogue among diverse audiences.

a) Intermediae by Arturo Franco, 2007:

Situated in the southern area of Matadero Madrid, this warehouse runs parallel to Paseo de la Chopera and spans from the water tank to the main entrance. Its expansive western facade, measuring over 270 meters in length, faces the main street, which serves as the organizing axis for the southern sector. This layout was designed to facilitate the seamless flow of the slaughter process across the various warehouses until its culmination in the cold rooms and subsequent sale on the street.

Fig.14 Position within the complex.

Image source available online at *Arquitectura Viva, Centro de Creación Matadero*. [21.02.2024].

Fig.15 Position within Hall 17.

Image source available online at *Veredes*. (n.d.), *Intermediae Matadero by Arturo Franco and Fabrice Van Teslaar* [20.03.2024].

Intermediae at Matadero Madrid is a hub for socially engaged artistic practices, promoting research and cultural innovation. Established in 2007, it has become a leading cultural venue, offering programs focusing on themes like ecology, childhood, civic engagement and the right to the city. With projects for local residents and collaborations with international scenes, Intermediae hosts lectures, exhibitions, and workshops, fostering open culture and accessibility, aiming to engage citizens in artistic and cultural activities.⁶⁶

⁶⁶ Intermediae, *Programs*, accessed at <https://www.mataderomadrid.org/en/programs/intermediae>. [21.02.2024]

Types of Strategies:

The intervention approach was primarily shaped by budgetary limitations and the expectation for the project to be temporary, set to be dismantled within two years. Warehouse 17, the first such intervention in the complex, served as a pilot, with the architect aiming for minimal alteration to explore non-intervention⁶⁷ and reversibility, fostering an ongoing dialogue between the new and the existing⁶⁸. The space's inherent linear typology, characteristic of industrial halls, dictates a specific rhythm for structural and opening elements. The project, a blend of insertion and installation strategies⁶⁹, seamlessly integrates with the original structure, ensuring its reversibility.

⁶⁷ *Intermediae, Matadero Madrid*, Archello. accessed at:
<https://archello.com/project/intermediae-matadero-madrid> [28.03.2024]

“The point was to contribute with a new attitude in face of the public realm of historical patrimony, a radical posture, an experience about limits, the limits of non-intervention, reducing such intervention to a bare minimum.”- *Description provided by the architects*

⁶⁸ *Ibidem*

“Against this, what is new: very few, very hard, very clean and very upright. The novelty appears with determination, sometimes very heavy, very confident; sometimes very clear, very fragile. Youthfulness looking to the past and vice versa.” - *Description provided by the architects*

⁶⁹ Brooker Graeme, Stone Sally, *Rereadings 2: Interior Architecture and the Design Principles of Remodelling Existing Buildings*, RIBA Publishing, 2018, ISBN 978 1 85946 581 3, Chapter 2 "Strategies."

Fig.16 Plan

Diagram made by the author on image base available online: Archello, *Intermediae - Matadero Madrid*, accessed [28.03.2024].

Fig.17 Cross-section of the entire volume

Diagram made by the author on image base available online: Archello, *Intermediae - Matadero Madrid*, accessed [28.03.2024].

For the interior volume, the architect placed a box made out of 20 mm varnished steel sheets and glass panels, slightly raised over the floor level and adjusted to the doorspace in its whole height. This volume serves the main purpose of the space such as events, discussions and exhibitions.

For the technical and sanitary spaces as well as the vestibule, the architect inserts another volume, this time opaque, made out of 10mm steel sheet.

Fig.18 Events Hall (Left) and the Entrance and Auxiliary Spaces (Right)
Photos by Carlos Fernández Piñar, (2006).

At the level of the floor, the concept relies on poured polished concrete, creating a seamless surface for the entire hall. This tactic can be arguably categorized as an intervention⁷⁰, due to its permanence.

For the furnishing, the project uses only steel profiles⁷¹ devoid of context or treatment and repurposes them as benches, bars, elevated floors, baseboards, doors, glass stops, and other elements, which is an interesting reference to this understanding of continuity between past and present, the character of the space being preserved.

Fig.19 Cross-Section of furnishing elements (left).
Fig.20 Photo of the Bar (right). Photo by Carlos Fernández Piñar, (2006).

⁷⁰ Brooker Graeme, Stone Sally, *Rereadings 2: Interior Architecture and the Design Principles of Remodelling Existing Buildings*, RIBA Publishing, 2018, ISBN 978 1 85946 581 3, Chapter 2 "Strategies."

⁷¹ *Intermediae, Matadero Madrid*, Archello. accessed at:
<https://archello.com/project/intermediae-matadero-madrid> [28.03.2024]

Although the interventions creating interior space can be characterized as insertions, they also maintain the aspect of an installation due to their reversibility.

Structure:

The project utilizes the hall's existing structure for the majority of the elements, positioning self-supporting insertions alongside it without directly connecting to the original elements, allowing them to co-exist independently. The original structure includes a supportive brick perimeter wall and an interior of regularly spaced reinforced concrete pillars.

For the glass insertions, I profile beams were embedded into the masonry every 3 meters, connecting to a U beam onto which the guide rails for the glass panels are attached. This is arguably one of the more intrusive new elements⁷².

Fig.21 Detail

Diagram made by the author on image base available online:
Archello, *Intermediae - Matadero Madrid*, accessed [28.03.2024].

⁷² *Intermediae, Matadero Madrid*, Archello, accessed at:
<https://archello.com/project/intermediae-matadero-madrid> [28.03.2024]

Fig.22 Nave 17 Historic Photo (left).

Image source: Madrid City Council, *Matadero. Memoria Histórica*.

Fig. 23 Intermediae (right).

Photo by Carlos Fernández Piñar, (2006).

Materiality:

The project's materiality stands out as a crucial aspect emphasized by Arturo Franco. Within the framework of "non-intervention," Franco deliberately maintained the appearance of the original hall, refraining from treating existing walls or repairing cuts and surface damage, thus showcasing the effects of time. The juxtaposition of new elements enhances the aesthetics of the old, and vice versa. Franco opted for raw materials like untreated steel profiles for the new elements, integrating them into the context while maintaining their distinctiveness, thereby reinforcing the concept of the passage of time. The intervention becomes a new phase of the hall, not necessarily its last.

The strategy deliberately avoids hiding the historical blemishes, such as the marks from radial saws on the walls or the impressions left by backhoes in the process of plaster removal. The PVC downspouts are intentionally left visible, as well as the cork used for insulation, serving as a testament to the building's history of refrigeration. In this instance the targeted interventions serve both as "band-aids" that mend the building's wounds and as displays that make the "scars" visible.⁷³

⁷³ *Intermediae, Matadero Madrid*, Archello. accessed at: <https://archello.com/project/intermediae-matadero-madrid> [28.03.2024]

"Thus, the past reveals itself, the work reveals itself. Any witness of the process remains intact." - *Description provided by the architects*

Fig.24 The use of materials.
Photos by Carlos Fernández Piñar, (2006).

Fig.25 Diagram-The use of materials.
Diagram made by the author on image base available online:
Archello, *Intermediae - Matadero Madrid*, accessed [06.04.2024].

Openings and Lighting:

The project makes use of the large and numerous openings of the existing hall, and relies heavily on natural light, the interior insertions do not touch the existing walls, thus facilitating lighting. For the artificial lighting, rows of incorporated spotlights were placed in a rhythm alternating the existing structure.

ig.26 Natural Light.

Diagram made by the author on image base available online:
Archello, *Intermediae - Matadero Madrid*, accessed [06.04.2024].

Fig.27 Natural Lighting and Artificial Lighting

Photos by Carlos Fernández Piñar, (2006).

Movement:

Movement within the space is sequential and linear, passing through a series of intermediate spaces from the entrance to the main events hall, where movement is not constrained.

Fig.28 Diagram Showing The Logic Of Movement.

Diagram made by the author on image base available online: Archello, *Intermediae - Matadero Madrid*, accessed [06.04.2024].

Conclusion:

In conclusion, the Intermediae project at Matadero Madrid has been a remarkable endeavor, showcasing both successes and challenges in its implementation. One of its key successes lies in its ability to transform a former industrial site into a vibrant cultural hub, fostering creativity and community engagement, without sanitizing the space beyond recognition, and losing touch with its uncomfortable past.

The project's emphasis on non-intervention has preserved the historical character of the space while allowing for contemporary interventions that enrich its cultural significance, adding another layer to the building's history.

Although initially conceived as a temporary intervention lasting a maximum of two years, the project's success is evident as it has become a permanent object within the Matadero Complex.

b) Nave 16 by Carnicero, Vila and Virseda Architects, 2012

Originally, pavilions 15 and 16 in the complex's southwest were designed for livestock stabling, display, and sale, near the railway for easy transfer to adjacent slaughterhouses. Their location in the widest part of the plot accommodated both stables/exhibitions and slaughterhouses efficiently.⁷⁴

Fig.29 Position within the complex.

Image source available online at *Arquitectura Viva, Centro de Creación Matadero*. [21.02.2024].

Following their cessation in 1996, both warehouses were rehabilitated under the guidance of architect Guillermo Costa⁷⁵. The renovation focused on the removal of internal partitions to establish open spaces, modernization of sanitation facilities, reinforcement of structural components, and restoration of the roofs and facades to their original state.

The current project is the result of an open call by the Madrid City Council in 2007, that wanted to convert the warehouse into a multifunctional space, dedicated to exhibitions, events and other functions. The theme required total flexibility of use, in order for the space to function as a “concert hall, conference hall, exhibition hall or as a fashion catwalk”, a mobile system was required in order for the hall to function as an integral space or as a set of smaller independent spaces.⁷⁶

⁷⁴ Servicio Histórico Coam, *Memoria Histórica Para El Proyecto De Rehabilitación Del Antiguo Matadero Municipal De Madrid, El Sector Meridional*, Madrid: COAM, enero, 2005.

⁷⁵ Ibidem.

⁷⁶ ArchDaily, *Nave 16 Matadero Madrid / ICA Arquitectura*, accessed at <https://www.archdaily.cl/cl/02-105564/nave-16-matadero-madrid-ica-arquitectura>. [28.03.2024]

Fig.30 Photos from Guillermo Costa's Intervention.
Image source: Madrid City Council, *Matadero. Memoria Histórica*.

Types of Strategies:

The strategy employed by the concept is primarily insertion⁷⁷, characterized by the essential incorporation of two flexible volumes within the existing halls. The structural integrity of the roof relies on the existing walls, while the movable system is contingent upon the roof's structure and the existing walls. The project still maintains its reversibility, due to the logic of the structure.

Fig.31 Exploded Axonometric View. Carnicero, Virseda, Vila, Nave 16 Matadero, Premio COAM, (2012).

⁷⁷ Brooker Graeme, Stone Sally, *Rereadings 2: Interior Architecture and the Design Principles of Remodelling Existing Buildings*, RIBA Publishing, 2018, ISBN 978 1 85946 581 3, Chapter 2 "Strategies."

Space Typologies:

Similar to the preceding case study, the spatial typology observed here is linear, originating from both the existing structure and the inserted volumes. Linear space offers versatility, ideal for hosting events, conferences, or exhibitions.⁷⁸

Fig.32 Plan of the Lower Level.

Diagram made by the author on image base available online at:
ArchDaily, *Nave 16 Matadero Madrid / ICA Arquitectura*, accessed [29.03.2024].

Fig.33 Plan of the Upper Level.

ArchDaily, *Nave 16 Matadero Madrid / ICA Arquitectura*, accessed [29.03.2024].

⁷⁸ ArchDaily, *Nave 16 Matadero Madrid / ICA Arquitectura*, accessed at <https://www.archdaily.cl/cl/02-105564/nave-16-matadero-madrid-ica-arquitectura>. [28.03.2024]

In 2009, budget constraints led to changes in the project. Sliding panels were replaced with steel doors, offering a more affordable solution. These doors, when opened, connect the central space with the surroundings, enhancing flexibility.

Fig.34 Cross-Section.

ArchDaily, *Nave 16 Matadero Madrid / ICA Arquitectura*, accessed [29.03.2024].

The Matadero pavilions, including Nave 16, are known for their symmetrical elevations, sections, and floor plans. This symmetry is particularly evident in the longitudinal section, where dividing it into the two large bays and three lower sections reveals vertical symmetry within each part, as well as overall symmetry across the entire structure.

Fig 35 Main Axis of Symmetry and Secondary Axes of Symmetry.

Diagram made by the author on image base available online at:
ArchDaily, *Nave 16 Matadero Madrid / ICA Arquitectura*, accessed [29.03.2024].

The new steel structure introduces patterns that reflect the original pavilion's design, disrupting its horizontality. Repetition is based on the spacing of top windows, influencing the layout of doors, pillars, and ventilation ducts, as well as the dimensions of the movable panels. Doors are twice the unit (top panel) size, pillars are spaced eight units (top panels) apart, and ducts align with windows every two units. The longitudinal section shows the entire section divided into 18 units, with truss connections every three units, dictated by the needs of the lower perimeter beam.

Fig.36 Logic of Dimensioning of the Panels

Diagram made by the author on image base available online at:
ArchDaily, *Nave 16 Matadero Madrid / ICA Arquitectura*, accessed [29.03.2024].

Fig.37 Repetition of the pattern. Photo by Roland Halbe (2007).

Diagram made by the author on image base available online at:
ArchDaily, *Nave 16 Matadero Madrid / ICA Arquitectura*, accessed [29.03.2024].

Structure:

The structure comprises six sections, featuring an open-plan layout within three clusters of eight interconnected naves, bisected by two taller, perpendicular sections. This configuration results in the facility being the largest in the Matadero complex, covering nearly 4,200 square meters and including 42 pens. The rehabilitation effort incorporates the metal trusses atop iron pillars and perimeter walls that are load-bearing, all organized around two major transverse bays. The roofing is designed with gabled ends, intersecting with smaller, also gabled roofs equipped with skylights, and set perpendicular to the two main larger roofs.

The project is based on a single structural idea, the movable system that is hung and dependent on the roof trusses and on the existing pillars.⁷⁹

FFig.38 Structure Of The Existing Building

Diagram made by the author on image base available online at:
ArchDaily, *Nave 16 Matadero Madrid / ICA Arquitectura*, accessed [05.04.2024].

The structure is split into upper and lower sections. For the upper part, truss reinforcement allows for hanging a perimeter beam to support the casement windows. Below, beams extending from the main bay to the pillars connect to a new lower perimeter beam, from which the door system is suspended. Additionally, braces between the upper and lower beams help redirect some loads from the columns to the truss, easing their stress.

⁷⁹ ArchDaily, *Nave 16 Matadero Madrid / ICA Arquitectura*, accessed at <https://www.archdaily.cl/cl/02-105564/nave-16-matadero-madrid-ica-arquitectura>. [28.03.2024]

Fig.39 Stress Diagram within the New Structure

Diagram made by the author on image base available online at:
ArchDaily, *Nave 16 Matadero Madrid / ICA Arquitectura*, accessed [05.04.2024].

Materiality:

The original construction materials for the pavilion included granite for the bases, exposed brick for the walls, and limestone masonry. Additionally, artificial stone was used for decorative elements, and tile work adorned the cornices and fascias.⁸⁰

Fig.40 Front View of Nave 16

Image source: Wikipedia. Photo by Vilacor.

⁸⁰ Servicio Histórico Coam, *Memoria Histórica Para El Proyecto De Rehabilitación Del Antiguo Matadero Municipal De Madrid, El Sector Meridional*, Madrid: COAM, enero, 2005.

The new project features significant additions of steel doors or panels, presented in dark gray or black, harmonizing with the existing structure, which was also painted black to ensure cohesion throughout the space. The flooring consists of polished concrete, subtly reflecting light and the structure above, providing a uniform base that ties the entire space together. Choosing black panels enhances the project's flexibility further, as the newly inserted volumes blend in seamlessly compared to lighter colors. The black backdrop provides an ideal setting for artistic performances or exhibitions.

Fig.50 Interior of Nave 16
Photos by Roland Halbe (2007).

Fig.51 Use of Materials

Diagram made by the author on image base available online at:
ArchDaily, Nave 16 Matadero Madrid / ICA Arquitectura, accessed [05.04.2024].

Openings and Lighting:

The taller design of the two main bays facilitates natural lighting within the complex, achieved through windows that span the entirety of this section's perimeter walls, allowing for ample light to penetrate the interior spaces.

The movable panels can be adjusted—opened or closed—based on the spatial requirements of different events. They can also be fully closed to create a pitch-black environment, ideal for projections or immersive experiences.⁸¹

Fig.52 Closed vs. Open
Photos by Roland Halbe (2007).

Fig.53 Natural Light

Diagram made by the author on image base available online at:
ArchDaily, *Nave 16 Matadero Madrid / ICA Arquitectura*, accessed [05.04.2024].

Movement:

When all panels are open, movement within the space is unrestricted, allowing free flow throughout. However, if the pavilion is divided into smaller exhibition areas using the panels, movement becomes sequential, guiding visitors through a curated path.

⁸¹ ArchDaily, *Nave 16 Matadero Madrid / ICA Arquitectura*, accessed at <https://www.archdaily.cl/cl/02-105564/nave-16-matadero-madrid-ica-arquitectura>. [29.03.2024]

Fig.54 Diagram Showing Different Positions Of The Panels

Diagram made by the author on image base available online at *Arquitectura Viva, Centro de Creación Matadero*, accessed [21.02.2024]

Fig.55 Diagram Showing Different Possibilities Of Movement Imposed By The Position Of The Panels.

Diagram made by the author on image base available online at: *ArchDaily, Nave 16 Matadero Madrid / ICA Arquitectura*, accessed [05.04.2024].

Conclusion:

The Nave 16 project exemplifies the successful adaptation of industrial heritage into a multifunctional space, blending historical preservation with modern needs. Its success lies in the flexibility offered by movable panels, allowing for diverse space configurations.

However, integrating modern functionality while preserving the building's character posed significant challenges, requiring a delicate balance between old and new and great attention to structural integrity.

Key lessons from Nave 16 emphasize the importance of flexibility and the innovative integration of contemporary elements that integrate the spatial logic and dimensioning of elements inspired by the existing building, without overshadowing the site's historical essence.

c) Casa del Lector by Ensemble Studio, 2012

Casa del Lector takes up three warehouses in the complex.

Ensamble Studio won the first prize in a 2006 competition aimed at restoring warehouses 13, 14, 17b, and 17c of the Old Slaughterhouse. The goal was to integrate a new educational program into the restored buildings.⁸²

Fig.56 Position within the complex

Image source available online at *Arquitectura Viva, Centro de Creación Matadero*. [21.02.2024].

Types of Strategies:

The project's strategy involves a deliberate intervention⁸³ characterized by purposeful alterations and additions to the existing structure of the hall. The architects opted to introduce two physical, perceptual, and activity levels. The upper level consists of precast beams weighing 40 tons each, inserted through the windows. This new layer of intervention serves as bridges between warehouses 13 and 14, which were previously independent buildings.⁸⁴ The lower level now follows the rhythm of the upper level. The intervention method

⁸² Ensemble Studio, *Casa del Lector*, ArchDaily. accessed at <https://www.archdaily.com/625763/casa-del-lector-ensamble-studio> [02.04.2024]

⁸³ Brooker Graeme, Stone Sally, *Rereadings 2: Interior Architecture and the Design Principles of Remodelling Existing Buildings*, RIBA Publishing, 2018, ISBN 978 1 85946 581 3, Chapter 2 "Strategies."

⁸⁴ Ensemble Studio, *Casa del Lector*, Divisare. accessed at <https://divisare.com/projects/284866-ensamble-studio-roland-halbe-casa-del-lector> [02.04.2024]

“And that buildings should be supported by this linkage, and connectivity should be the basic principle of the system. Our intention was hence to materialize this network of connections and build bridges towards reading. Reader’s House will give life to the bond between people and reading”

employed at all levels of the project signifies its irreversibility, a departure from previous studies, with various elements discussed in subsequent sections.

Fig. 57 Exploded Axonometric View

Image source available online at
ArchDaily, *Casa del Lector / Ensemble Studio*, accessed [04.04.2024]

Fig.58 Casa del Lector Exterior (left) and Fig. 59 Interior (right).

Photos by Roland Halbe (2012).

Fig.60 Casa del Lector Functional Diagram

Fig.61 Casa del Lector Functional Diagram - Cross Section

Fig.62 Casa del Lector Functional Diagram - Cross Section

Diagrams made by the author on image bases available online at ArchDaily, *Casa del Lector* / *Ensamble Studio*, accessed [04.04.2024]

Space Typologies:

Like the previous case study, the spatial layout observed here is linear, derived from both the original structure and the added volumes. However, the character of the space is altered, introducing a new rhythm. Instead of the long uninterrupted space of the warehouses, the area is now divided into shorter linear spaces, perpendicular to the original axis of the existing structures. The lower level aligns with the rhythm set by the upper level, which is dictated by the windows of the existing structure, creating a mutual dependence where openings become solid and vice versa. This dynamic and adaptable level accommodates educational and cultural activities⁸⁵. The space is furthermore segmented, by the insertion of different volumes hosting administrative spaces, storage rooms, technical rooms and sanitary spaces. The office area is located in warehouse 17c, whereas warehouse 17b serves as a multipurpose room or auditorium.

Fig.63 Space Typologies First Level(left) and Upper Level (right)

Diagram made by the author on image base available online at ArchDaily, *Casa del Lector / Ensemble Studio*, accessed [04.04.2024]

⁸⁵ ArchDaily, *Casa del Lector / Ensemble Studio*, accessed at <https://www.archdaily.com/625763/casa-del-lector-ensemble-studio>. [04.04.2024]

Structure:

The majority of the original structure is retained for the project, the original masonry, steel trusses and pillars, with the exception of the pitched roof of the auditorium (nave 17b), which is rebuilt to maintain the original profile while imposing a different order. An arc created by aluminum strips encloses and enhances the interior space.⁸⁶

Fig. 64 Roof Structure of the Auditorium

Image source available online at ArchDaily, *Casa del Lector / Ensemble Studio*, accessed [04.04.2024]

The bridges formed by the precast beams in the halls 13 and 14 are supported by two concrete pillars positioned at the lower part of each corresponding opening. Concrete reinforcement of the exterior walls was also required, carried out on the interior surface.

Fig.65 Insertion of the Beams (left)

Fig.66 Photo from the Process (right). Photo by Roland Halbe (2013).

⁸⁶Ibidem [04.04.2024]

The remaining inserted volumes either rely on the existing structure, enclosing around the existing pillars or walls, or are independent structures positioned beneath the existing structure or the new bridges.

Fig.67 Photos from the Construction Site. Photos by Roland Halbe (2013).

Fig.68 Diagram Showing Stresses In Structural Elements

Diagram made by the author on image base available online at ArchDaily, *Casa del Lector / Ensemble Studio*, accessed [04.04.2024]

Materiality:

The materiality of this project diverges significantly from the previous case studies within the Matadero Madrid complex. This contrast may be attributed to both program requirements and the influence of the newly added structure. While the project employs similar materials for the new elements—concrete, steel, and glass—it does so in a distinct manner. The interior, including the existing hall structure, is characterized by plastered and painted surfaces in sterile white, creating a uniform appearance. Raw concrete is utilized for the precast elements, introducing a stark contrast to the white and other materials, thus adding a new dimension to the project's language. Glass and white glazed panels enclose the additional

volumes, while light gray steel sheets are used for frames, maintaining a consistent palette throughout. The only notable contrast is provided by vertical circulations, which feature steel and glass elements painted in bright red. Furnishing elements, in vibrant colors of yellow, red, and green, further enhance this contrast. Exhibition panels follow a similar construction logic as the walls, employing gray steel frames.

Fig.69 Materials and Use of Color.

Photos by Roland Halbe (2013).

Openings and Lighting:

Similar to the other case studies, this project utilizes the existing openings and skylights, emphasizing natural lighting throughout the space. The light reflects off the interior white surfaces, enhancing the brightness of the space and creating an environment conducive to reading, exhibitions, events, and conferences.

Fig.70 Natural Light

Diagram made by the author on image base available online at ArchDaily, *Casa del Lector / Ensemble Studio*, accessed [04.04.2024]

Fig.71 Natural Light

Photo by Roland Halbe (2013).

Movement:

The project alters the movement logic by introducing a second level perpendicular to the existing axis, as well as vertical circulations, connecting the interior spaces of warehouses 13 and 14. This creates a more intricate movement pattern, similar to a matrix, compared to the linear movement along the original warehouse axis; two different planes of movement intersect on 2 levels, creating a dynamic image.

Fig.72 Logic of Movement

Diagram made by the author on image base available online at ArchDaily, *Casa del Lector / Ensamble Studio*, accessed [04.04.2024]

Conclusion:

The project's approach differs notably from the previous case studies, potentially subject to critique within the context of uncomfortable heritage. This approach sanitizes the space, distancing it from its past, possibly influenced by the program's aim to create a more kid- and young adult-friendly environment. Apart from the facade and the interior trusses and pillars, there are no visible indications of the space's former identity as a slaughterhouse.

Fig.73 Multiple Uses of the Inserted Beams

Image source available online at

ArchDaily, *Casa del Lector* / *Ensamble Studio*, accessed [04.04.2024]

6. Analysis

6.1 Comparison of the different case studies

Matadero Madrid serves as an exemplary model for addressing industrial sites within the framework of challenging heritage, encompassing both physical and non-physical perspectives. This includes its approach to architectural coherence throughout the complex, engagement with local authorities, cultural institutions, heritage preservation policies, and community involvement.

The three case studies selected—Intermediae by Arturo Franco, Nave 16 by ICA Architecture, and Casa del Lector by Ensemble Studio—exhibit markedly different strategies and approaches to preservation and adaptive reuse. Each case study demonstrates a unique understanding of reconversion, influenced in part by the specific program requirements of the respective venues.

While Intermediae and Nave 16 share similarities in their versatile functions, accommodating various events and exhibitions while maintaining flexibility, Casa del Lector presents a more complex program as a Mediateque. This entails more stringent building requirements such as thermal and humidity control etc., as well as a diverse range of spaces. While Casa del Lector also incorporates flexibility in some areas, the program necessitates a more structured framework, evident in the intervention strategy employed and the irreversibility of the proposed changes.

6.2 Identification of common themes and patterns

The architects of Intermediae and Nave 16 share a similar approach to preserving history while revealing the building's past through intervention. Rather than sanitizing the space beyond recognition, they allow different layers of history to emerge through new insertions.

This is particularly evident in Arturo Franco's Intermediae, where a method of non-intervention maintains the building's imperfections, enabling visitors to envision its former use as a slaughterhouse and refrigerating plant. Nave 16 follows a similar path, although with some distinctions; ICA Architecture proposes a more extensive restoration process, nearly reversing the building's damages entirely. Their project respects the warehouse's uncomfortable past more subtly, employing industrial materials and colors and closely aligning newly added elements with existing rhythms.

In contrast, Casa del Lector integrates industrial elements and references differently. As previously discussed, the project adopts a completely different language that sanitizes the space and transforms the atmosphere into a kid-friendly environment. While this approach may face criticism, it is understandable considering the program's requirements.

Similarities can be observed among the case studies in their incorporation of industrial references and the consistent use of materials such as steel elements, glass panels, and polished concrete.

6.3 Evaluation of the effectiveness of reconversion strategies

The success of these projects is evident, as they have all stood the test of time and become integral components of Matadero Madrid, showcasing their effectiveness.

They stand as remarkable examples of European architecture and exemplary projects of adaptive-reuse.

6.4 Assessment of the sustainability and long-term viability of reconversion projects

Firstly, the sustainability of adaptive reuse in the case studies is evident, thereby reducing resource consumption and minimizing waste. Additionally, the integration of sustainable design features, such as energy-efficient systems and materials, promotes environmental responsibility. The success and longevity of these projects also depend on their ability to meet evolving community needs and remain relevant over time. Furthermore, financial viability plays a crucial role, requiring careful planning to ensure ongoing maintenance and operational costs can be sustained. Community engagement and support are essential for the continued success of these spaces, as they rely on public participation and patronage to thrive. Matadero's current setup has contributed to its success, placing it among the top 10 cultural institutions in Spain that have persevered through the financial crisis.

The success of the complex is evident, with an average of over 500,000 visitors per year for music, art events and avant-garde plays.⁸⁷

7. Discussion

7.1 Interpretation of the findings in relation to the research objectives

The thesis examined the adaptive reuse of the chosen case studies, emphasizing their importance in urban development and heritage preservation, particularly in dealing with "uncomfortable heritage." It explored the dual objective of maintaining the historical integrity of industrial structures while adapting them to new functions. Through in-depth case studies, the research revealed the complexities of revitalizing industrial spaces while respecting their historical and cultural significance, as well as acknowledging the discomfort associated with their previous roles.

⁸⁷ Minder, Raphael, *At Matadero, Red Bull Adds Money and Energy to Culture*, The New York Times, 2013, accessed at <https://www.nytimes.com/2013/09/24/arts/design/at-matadero-red-bull-adds-money-and-energy-to-culture.html> [07.04.2024]

This recognition comes from the Culture Observatory, a Madrid-based nonprofit organization that monitors cultural spending and consults a panel of arts experts to identify standout performers.

Research Objectives

- a) What are the main challenges and dilemmas associated with the adaptive reuse of uncomfortable heritage sites, particularly in terms of preserving their historical significance while accommodating contemporary needs?

The principal challenges and dilemmas linked to the subject, as demonstrated in the case studies, entail striking a balance between the new intervention and preserving the historical layers of the existing building, while also accommodating contemporary functional requirements. Additionally, challenges arise from budget constraints, as well as the involvement of municipal authorities, the local community, and urban regulations. The study unveiled that the success of such interventions often hinges on a bottom-up approach.

- b) What are the key factors influencing decision-making processes and stakeholder engagement in the reconversion of uncomfortable heritage sites?

The primary factors influencing decisions regarding these types of projects include the municipality's approach to the situation and its response to public pressure or opinion. In the case of Matadero, the municipality, along with several cultural institutions, adopted a bottom-up approach by involving the community in discussions about the future of the complex. Public architecture competitions further underscore this approach.

- c) What are the most effective adaptive reuse strategies for industrial building sites classified as uncomfortable heritage, considering factors such as cultural sensitivity, environmental sustainability, and economic viability?

The most effective approaches, as exemplified in the case studies, prioritize flexibility and perceive the new intervention as merely one phase in the building's ongoing existence. Successful interventions acknowledge the dynamic nature of their programs, adapting to changes as needed.

Indeed, sustainability must be at the heart of design to ensure success.

Matadero Madrid has forged corporate partnerships, with private entities investing in complex refurbishments and programming in exchange for rent-free space.

Through such collaborations and revenue diversification efforts, Matadero has shown resilience against budget constraints and government austerity. Additionally, its proactive approach to securing alternative funding sources, such as international co-productions and embassy collaborations, underscores its commitment to long-term sustainability amid broader challenges in the cultural sector.

- d) How do different case studies of adaptive reuse projects on uncomfortable heritage sites compare in terms of their approaches, outcomes, and impacts on the surrounding communities?

The response to this research question was detailed in Chapter 6, Analysis.

7.2 Limitations of the study and suggestions for future research

While the study offers valuable insights, it is constrained by several limitations, primarily its focus on the Matadero Madrid example. Moreover, it is further restricted to only three case studies. This suggests a necessity for future research to investigate a wider range of projects from various countries and cultural backgrounds, as well as diverse urban regulatory frameworks.

8. Conclusion

In conclusion, the analysis of the three case studies within the framework of Matadero Madrid provides valuable insights into the adaptive reuse of industrial sites and the preservation of uncomfortable heritage. Each case study demonstrates unique approaches to reconversion, influenced by program requirements and historical context.

Despite challenges such as budget constraints and community involvement, the success of these projects highlights their effectiveness in revitalizing industrial spaces while maintaining historical integrity. Moving forward, future research should explore a broader array of projects from different countries and cultural contexts to further enhance our understanding of adaptive reuse strategies and their long-term sustainability.

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